

College of Dentistry – University of Baghdad**Patient Information Sheet**

You are invited to participate in a scientific research. Please take your time to read the following information carefully before you decide whether or not you wish to participate. You can ask for clarifications or any more information about the study from the researcher and you can discuss this with outsiders.

Information about the research (to be written by the researcher in a simple language answering the following questions when applicable)

1. Study title “Posterior Palatal Seal recording: Fact and Reasons Among Iraqi Dentists”
2. What is the purpose of this study? was to assess Iraqi dentists in their knowledge and application of the post-dam in maxillary complete dentures.
3. Where will the study be conducted? Prosthodontics Department /College Of Dentistry/ Baghdad university
4. What are the procedures to be followed and what will you be asked to do at each visit? Questionnaires were distributed randomly through online Google Forms
5. How long will the participation in the study last? 10-15 minutes
6. If you decided to taking part in the study, will the treatment be different from the treatment you would get otherwise? No
7. Who should not enter the study? Any Dentist
8. What will be the benefits of the study?
 - a) To the participant? Nothing
 - b) To the investigator? Research data
9. What are the possible risks of taking part? None.
10. If you feel severe discomfort or pain during the study, would you be able to take any relief medication? No need.
11. Will your participation in the study interfere with your daily activities? No.
12. Will you be informed of the results of the study? No.

If you agree to participate in this study, we will ensure your confidentiality with no one except the study researchers have the right to access your dental (medical) notes.

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary and you are free to refuse to take part or to withdraw from the study at any time without having to give a reason and without this affecting your future medical care or your relationship with medical staff looking after you.

Thank you for reading this Information Sheet and considering your participation in this study

Consent Form

	Please tick to confirm
I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without any medical/dental care affected.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that relevant sections of my medical notes and data collected during the study may be looked at by individuals from the College of Dentistry – University of Baghdad where it is relevant to my taking part in this research. I give permission to these individuals to have access to my records.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree to take part in the above study.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Regarding any information and records taken during the research please specify your acceptance to share them as you desire:					
	Personal data	X-rays	Extra-oral photographs	Intra-oral photographs	Others
Confidential	<input type="checkbox"/>				
For consultation	<input type="checkbox"/>				
For teaching	<input type="checkbox"/>				
For conferences	<input type="checkbox"/>				
For publication	<input type="checkbox"/>				

	Name	Signature	Date
Participant			
Parent/guardian (if appropriate)			
Person taking consent			

Person to contact:

Name:

Phone No.:

Email: